

ASSESSMENT OF KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND PRACTICES REGARDING USE OF SANITARY PADS VERSUS MENSTRUAL CUP AMONG WOMEN IN SELECTED CITY IN VIEW TO DEVELOP AN INFORMATION BOOKLET.

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ABSTRACT:

INTRODUCTION:

Menstruation, a natural biological process, is still stigmatized in many communities. This study aimed to assess and compare the knowledge, attitude, and practices (KAP) of women using sanitary pads (SP) versus menstrual cups (MC) in selected cities, promoting sustainable menstrual hygiene.

OBJECTIVES:

1. To assess the prevalence of use of sanitary pads and menstrual cup among women in selected city.
2. To compare the knowledge, attitude and practices regarding use of sanitary pads and menstrual cup among women in selected city.
3. To find out the association between study findings with selected demographic variables.

METHOD:

The present study adopted a quantitative research approach and utilized a comparative descriptive non-experimental research design to investigate the topic. The research was conducted in selected areas of the city over a period of 28 days. The population targeted for this study comprised reproductive-age women residing in these selected areas, who met the defined inclusion criteria. From this population, the sample included women who were either users of menstrual cups or sanitary pads. A non-probability purposive sampling technique was employed to select participants. Initially, the researcher surveyed 200 women, of

whom 84 were using menstrual cups and 116 were using sanitary pads. From this pool, a purposive selection was made to include 50 users of menstrual cups and 50 users of sanitary pads, achieving a total sample size of 100 participants. The selection was based on the availability of participants and their suitability as per the inclusion criteria. For data analysis, both descriptive and inferential statistical methods were used to interpret the findings.

RESULTS:

MC users showed significantly higher knowledge (74% vs 44%), more positive attitudes (100% vs 42%), and better practices (78% vs 22%) than SP users. SP prevalence was 58%, MC 42%.

Demographic variables had minimal influence.

CONCLUSION:

Women using menstrual cups demonstrated better awareness and hygiene practices. Promoting menstrual cups can support healthier, eco-friendly menstrual care.

KEYWORDS: Sanitary pad, Menstrual cup, Knowledge, Attitude, Practice.

INTRODUCTION:

Celebrating Menstruation: A Natural and Sustainable Shift

Menstruation is a natural and vital aspect of women's health, symbolizing fertility and resilience. However, cultural stigma and environmental concerns surrounding menstrual hygiene products remain significant, especially in India, where 336 million women menstruate and 121 million rely on single-use sanitary pads. These pads generate approximately 9,000 tons of non-biodegradable waste annually, posing serious health and environmental risks.¹

While menstrual health and hygiene (MHH) awareness has grown supported by initiatives like the National Health Mission (2011) and Swachh Bharat Mission most women still depend on sanitary pads. The latest NFHS-5 (2019–2021) shows that 77.6% of Indian women use hygienic protection, yet menstrual cup adoption remains at just 0.3%. Promoting sustainable alternatives like menstrual cups, through education and accessibility especially in rural areas can lead to healthier choices and a cleaner environment. This research explores current practices, challenges, and opportunities in menstrual hygiene management, advocating for a shift towards more sustainable solutions.²

Menstrual hygiene is a crucial aspect of women's reproductive health. Access to safe and affordable menstrual hygiene products is essential for maintaining comfort, dignity, and overall well-being during menstruation. Sanitary pads have traditionally been the most common option, but menstrual cups are gaining popularity as an alternative. Despite being a normal and necessary aspect of a woman's life, menstruation is nevertheless taboo in many cultures. Reproductive tract infections, cervical cancer, and social isolation are just a few of the health and social issues that can result from a lack of knowledge and instruction regarding menstrual cleanliness and management. Alternative menstrual products, including menstrual cups, have gained popularity recently since they provide a more environmentally friendly and sustainable alternative to conventional sanitary pads. Understanding the current practices in menstrual hygiene management is important. This includes examining the usage patterns, frequency of pad changes, disposal methods, and associated challenges. It helps identify whether women are using these products correctly and whether their current practices are satisfactory. It is essential to evaluate their awareness of the available options, including the differences in composition, usage, and potential benefits or risks associated with each product. Identifying any knowledge gaps will help in designing appropriate educational interventions.³

METHODS:

The research methodology adopted for this study was a quantitative research approach, the comparative descriptive non-experimental research design was used for this study. This was based on “rosentoch and beker’s health belief model”. The accessible population selected for this study consisted of women of selected cities who are using sanitary pads and menstrual cups. To find out the prevalence rate of sanitary pads and menstrual cups researcher did a survey of 200 women and after that researcher took the desired samples for study. The sample size was 100 in that 50 women who were Sanitary pad and 50 women who were using Menstrual cup. The sample size was calculated using power analysis formula.

The formula used for sample size is –

$$n = Z_{\alpha/2} * p * (1-p) / MOE^2$$

Sample were selected as per inclusion criteria using a non-probability purposive sampling technique. The tool consists of demographic data and a self-structured knowledge questionnaire related to Sanitary pad and Menstrual cup, a Likert rating scale for the attitude of Sanitary pad and menstrual cup, and a checklist to know the practices of Sanitary pad and menstrual cup. The data was collected from 25/12/2024 to 20/01/2025. Before the data collection consent was taken from the participants. Collected data is analysed by using descriptive and inferential statistics. Analysis of demographic data was done by frequency and percentage. Two sample z-tests were used to compare the findings of knowledge attitude and practices of sanitary pads and menstrual cups and Fisher’s exact test was used to find out the association between knowledge attitude and practice of sanitary pads and menstrual cups with selected demographic variables.

RESULTS:

Demographic differences of the study show that Sanitary pad users are mostly housewives and students, with lower income. Menstrual cup users are mostly students and private employees, with higher income and education.

200 women were surveyed for the use of sanitary pads and menstrual cups. The prevalence of use of sanitary pads was 58% and the prevalence of use of menstrual cups was 42% (Table 1)

Two sample z-tests for the comparison of knowledge among women in menstrual cups and sanitary pads. The average knowledge score in the sanitary pads group was 6.3 which is 7.4 in the menstrual cup group. The Z-value for this test was 3.4. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected. The average knowledge score in menstrual cups is significantly more than that in sanitary pads. Knowledge regarding menstrual cups was significantly more than that regarding sanitary pads among women. (Table 2)

Two sample z-tests for the comparison of attitudes of women toward the use of menstrual cups and sanitary pads. The average attitude score towards the use of sanitary pads group was 25.2 which is 33.2 towards the use of menstrual cups. The Z-value for this test was 20. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected. The attitude score among women toward the use of menstrual cups is significantly more than that attitude score towards the use of sanitary pads. (Table 3)

Two sample z-tests for the comparison of practices among women regarding the use of menstrual cups and sanitary pads. The average practice score regarding the use of sanitary pads group was 5.6 which was 7.2 regarding the use of menstrual cups. The Zvalue for this test was 4.3. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected. The practice score among women regarding the use of menstrual cups is significantly more than the practice score regarding the use of sanitary pads. (Table 4)

Fisher's exact test was used to find out the association of knowledge, attitude and practices of sanitary pad and menstrual cup. Association of knowledge among women regarding the use of sanitary pads with selected demographic. Since all the p-values were large (greater than 0.05), none of the demographic variables was found to have significant association with the knowledge among women regarding use of sanitary pads. (Table 5)

Association of attitude among women towards the use of sanitary pads with selected demographic variables Since all the p-values were large (greater than 0.05), none of the demographic variables was found to have a significant association with the attitude among women towards the use of sanitary pads. (Table 6)

Association of practices among women towards the use of sanitary pads with selected demographic variables Since the p-values corresponding to age, occupation, and Duration of use of sanitary pads were small (less than 0.05), the demographic variables age, occupation, and Duration of use of sanitary pads were found to have a significant association with the practices among women regarding the use of sanitary pads. (Table 7)

Association of knowledge among women regarding the use of menstrual cups with selected demographic variables Since the p-value corresponding to Duration of use of menstrual cup was small (less than 0.05), the demographic variable Duration of use of menstrual cup was found to have significant association with the knowledge among women regarding the use of menstrual cup. (Table 8)

Association of practices among women regarding the use of menstrual cups with selected demographic variables Since all the p-values were large (greater than 0.05), none of the demographic variable was found to have significant association with the practices among women regarding the use of menstrual cup. (Table 9)

Irrespective of demography, all the women had positive attitudes towards the use of menstrual cups.

ANALYSIS OF DATA:

1. Description of samples (women) based on their characteristics.

In the sanitary pad group, 38% of the women were age 15-25 years, 32% of them had age 25.1-35 years and 30% of them had age 35.1-45 years. In the menstrual cup group, 28% of the women had age 15-25 years, 40% of them had age 25.1-35 years and 32% of them had age 35.1-45 years.

In the sanitary pad group, 24% of the women had primary education, 38% of them had secondary education, 22% of them had higher secondary education and 16% of them had graduated. In the menstrual cup group, 2% had primary education, 22% of them had secondary education, 30% of them had higher secondary education and 46% of them had graduated.

In the sanitary pad group, 46% of them were housewives 38% of them were students and 16% were private employees. In the menstrual cup group, 18% of them were housewives 32% of them were students, 22% of them were government employees and 28% of them were private employees.

In sanitary pads, 46% of them had a monthly income of Rs.20000-30000, 26% of them had income Rs. 30000-40000 and 28% of them had income Rs. 40000-50000. In menstrual cup, 40% of them had monthly income Rs.20000-30000, 42% of them had income Rs. 30000-40000 and 18% of them had income Rs. 40000-50000.

In the sanitary pad group, 2% of them were using sanitary pads for up to 5 years, 40% of them were using them for 6-10 years, 24% of them were using them for 11-15 years, 14% of them were using it for 16-20 years and 20% of them were using it for more than 20 years. In the menstrual cup group, 96% of them were using menstrual cups for up to 5 years and 4% of them were using menstrual cups for 6-10 years

2. Analysis of data related to the prevalence of use of sanitary pads and menstrual cups among women in selected cities.

Table 2.1: Table showing the distribution of Prevalence of use of sanitary pads and menstrual cups among women in the selected city

n =200

Use	Number of women	Prevalence
Menstrual cup	84	42.0%
Sanitary pad	116	58.0%

Figure No. 2.1: Pie diagram showing percentage-wise distribution of prevalence of sanitary pads and menstrual cups.

200 women were surveyed for the use of sanitary pads and menstrual cups. The prevalence of use of sanitary pads was 58% and the prevalence of use of menstrual cups was 42%

3. Analysis of data related to the comparison of knowledge, attitude, and practices regarding the use of sanitary pads and menstrual cups among women

Table 3.1: Table showing distribution Knowledge regarding the use of sanitary pads and menstrual cups among women

n =50, 50

Knowledge	Sanitary Pad		Menstrual cup	
	Freq	%	Freq	%
Poor	2	4%	1	2%
Average	26	52%	12	24%
Good	22	44%	37	74%

Figure No. 3.1: Bar diagram showing percentage-wise distribution of knowledge of sanitary pads and menstrual cups.

In the sanitary pad group, 4% of the women had poor knowledge, 52% of them had average knowledge and 44% of them had good knowledge regarding the use of sanitary pads. In the menstrual cup group, 2% of them had poor knowledge, 24% of them had average knowledge and 74% of them had good knowledge regarding menstrual cups.

Table 3.2 Table showing the distribution of two sample z-tests for the comparison of knowledge among women in menstrual cups and sanitary pads.

n =50, 50

Group	Mean	SD	z	p-value
Sanitary Pad	6.3	1.5	3.4	0.000
Menstrual cup	7.4	1.7		

Figure No. 3.2 Bar diagram showing the distribution of average score of knowledge of sanitary pads and menstrual cups.

The researcher applied Two sample z-tests for the comparison of knowledge among women in menstrual cups and sanitary pads. The average knowledge score in the sanitary pads group was 6.3 which is 7.4 in the menstrual cup group. The Z-value for this test was 3.4. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected. The average knowledge score in menstrual cups is significantly more than that in sanitary pads. Knowledge regarding menstrual cups was significantly more than that regarding sanitary pads among women.

Table 3.3: Table showing distribution of Attitudes towards the use of sanitary pads and menstrual cups among women

n =50, 50

Attitude	Sanitary Pad		Menstrual cup	
	Freq	%	Freq	%
Negative	29	58%	0	0%
Positive	21	42%	50	100%

Figure No. 3.3: Bar diagram showing the distribution of attitudes towards the use of sanitary pads and menstrual cups.

58% of the women had negative attitude and 42% of them had positive attitudes towards the use of sanitary pads. All of the women in menstrual cup group had positive attitude towards the use of menstrual cup.

Table 3.4 Table showing distribution of two sample z-tests for the comparison of attitudes among women towards the use of menstrual cups and sanitary pads.

n =50, 50

Group	Mean	SD	z	p-value
Sanitary Pad	25.2	2.4	20	0.000
Menstrual cup	33.2	1.5		

Figure No. 3.4 Bar diagram showing the distribution of attitude scores regarding the use of sanitary pads and menstrual cups.

The researcher applied Two sample z-tests for the comparison of attitudes of women toward the use of menstrual cups and sanitary pads. The average attitude score towards the use of sanitary pads group was 25.2 which is 33.2 towards the use of menstrual cups. The Z-value for this test was 20. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected. The attitude score among women toward the use of menstrual cups is significantly more than that attitude score towards the use of sanitary pads.

Table 3.5: Table showing distribution of practices regarding the use of sanitary pads and menstrual cups among women

n =50, 50

Practices	Sanitary Pad		Menstrual cup	
	Freq	%	Freq	%
Poor	2	4%	2	4%
Average	37	74%	9	18%
Good	11	22%	39	78%

Figure No.3.5 Bar diagram showing the distribution of practices regarding the use of sanitary pads and menstrual cups.

4% of the women had poor practices, 74% of them had average practices and 22% of them had good practices regarding the use of sanitary pad. 4% of the women had poor practices, 18% of them had average practices and 78% of them had good practices regarding the use of menstrual cup.

Table 3.6: Table showing distribution of two sample z-tests for the comparison of practice scores among women regarding the use of menstrual cups and sanitary pads.

n =50, 50

Group	Mean	SD	z	p-value
Sanitary Pad	5.6	2.1	4.3	0.000
Menstrual cup	7.2	1.7		

Figure No. 3.6 Bar diagram showing the distribution of practice scores regarding the use of sanitary pads and menstrual cups

The researcher applied Two sample z-tests for the comparison of practices among women regarding the use of menstrual cups and sanitary pads. The average practice score regarding the use of sanitary pads group was 5.6 which was 7.2 regarding the use of menstrual cups. The Z-value for this test was 4.3. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected. The practice score among women regarding the use of menstrual cups is significantly more than the practice score regarding the use of sanitary pads.

DISCUSSION:

The present study revealed that while sanitary pads remain the most widely used menstrual product, women using menstrual cups demonstrated higher knowledge, more positive attitudes, and better practices. These findings align with Van Eijk et al. (2019)⁴ and Weerawatsopon et al. (2021)⁵, who also reported greater satisfaction and health benefits among menstrual cup users, though adoption remains low due to limited awareness and cultural barriers. Similar to studies by Choudhary (2018)⁶ and Kattimani (2024)⁷, our results highlight that sanitary pads are widely preferred for their accessibility, but they pose environmental and health concerns. Conversely, menstrual cups were viewed more favorably once accurate information was provided. The implications are clear: while sanitary pads remain dominant, increasing awareness of menstrual cups could promote safer, cost-effective, and environmentally sustainable menstrual hygiene practices.

CONCLUSION:

This study assessed the knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding the use of sanitary pads versus menstrual cups among women in a selected city. The findings showed that while sanitary pads are still the most commonly used product, women using menstrual cups demonstrated significantly higher knowledge, more positive attitudes, and better hygienic practices. No significant association was found between most demographic variables and knowledge, attitude, or practice, except for age, occupation, and duration of use in relation to sanitary pad practices. The results suggest that although cultural familiarity and accessibility sustain the widespread use of sanitary pads, menstrual cups offer clear advantages in terms of health, cost-effectiveness, and environmental sustainability. Overall, the study highlights the importance of strengthening menstrual health education and promoting sustainable alternatives such as menstrual cups to improve women's reproductive health outcomes and reduce environmental burden.

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